

Participant ID:

Questionnaire

The SAFER Wearables Study

A study of the acceptability and performance of wearables for atrial fibrillation screening in older adults.

Instructions

We would be grateful for your feedback on how you found wearing the devices. It will help us understand how to improve them for future patients. It takes about 15 minutes.

Please complete this questionnaire when you finish wearing the devices. Then place it in the packaging with the devices, ready to be sent back to the study team.

Contact Us

If you have any questions please contact the study team:

Phone: contact us using the following number during working hours (Monday to Friday 9am – 5pm): **01223 331 063**. If we miss your call or if you call outside these hours, there is an answer phone on this number. If you leave a message we will respond to you at the earliest opportunity.

Email: safer-wearables@medschl.cam.ac.uk

Please answer as many questions as you can.

1. What day did you start wearing the devices on?

Please tick one box

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
Started on							

2. What day did you finish wearing each device on?

Please tick one box for each device (shown in the pictures below)

	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
chest-patch							
wristband							
watch							

3. If you removed any device before the end, then why?

I didn't remove them before the end

I removed the chest-patch because:

I removed the wristband because:

I removed the watch because:

Chest-patch

Wristband

Watch

Feedback on the study

Please tick one answer for each statement.

4. Wearing the devices made me feel safer.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

5. My friends or relatives encouraged me to keep wearing the devices.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

6. The researchers encouraged me to keep wearing the devices.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

7. I didn't like friends or relatives seeing me wearing the devices.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

8. I didn't see any benefit to future patients from me wearing the devices.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

Please turn over

Feedback on the chest-patch

Please tick one answer for each statement about the chest-patch.

9. The chest-patch was easy to put on.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

10. The chest-patch was easy to remove.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

11. It was easy to move about while wearing the chest-patch.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

12. Wearing the chest-patch disturbed my sleep.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

13. The chest-patch didn't interfere with my daily activities (washing, dressing, eating, going to the toilet etc).

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

14. The chest-patch was unhygienic.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

15. The weight of the chest-patch was not a problem.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

16. The chest-patch made me feel sweaty.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

17. The chest-patch was too tight.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

18. The chest-patch was uncomfortable.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

19. The chest-patch came off accidentally.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

20. I was aware of the chest-patch when I was wearing it.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

21. I have worn devices like the chest-patch before.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

22. Wearing the chest-patch was stressful.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

23. If the chest-patch was regularly used to check people's health then I would be happy to wear it for a week.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

24. The sticky dots on my chest didn't bother me.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

Please turn over

Feedback on the wristband

Please tick one answer for each statement about the wristband.

25. The wristband was easy to put on.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

26. The wristband was easy to remove.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

27. It was easy to move about while wearing the wristband.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

28. Wearing the wristband disturbed my sleep.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

29. The wristband didn't interfere with my daily activities (washing, dressing, eating, going to the toilet etc).

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

30. The wristband was unhygienic.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

31. The weight of the wristband was not a problem.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

32. The wristband made me feel sweaty.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

33. The wristband was too tight.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

34. The wristband was uncomfortable.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

35. The wristband came off accidentally.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

36. I was aware of the wristband when I was wearing it.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

37. I have worn devices like the wristband before.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

38. Wearing the wristband was stressful.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

39. If the wristband was regularly used to check people's health then I would be happy to wear it for a week.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

Please turn over

Feedback on the watch

Please tick one answer for each statement about the watch.

40. The watch was easy to put on.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

41. The watch was easy to remove.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

42. It was easy to move about while wearing the watch.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

43. Wearing the watch disturbed my sleep.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

44. The watch didn't interfere with my daily activities (washing, dressing, eating, going to the toilet etc).

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

45. The watch was unhygienic.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

46. The weight of the watch was not a problem.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

47. The watch made me feel sweaty.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

48. The watch was too tight.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

49. The watch was uncomfortable.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

50. The watch came off accidentally.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

51. I was aware of the watch when I was wearing it.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

52. I have worn devices like the watch before.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

53. Wearing the watch was stressful.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

54. If the watch was regularly used to check people's health then I would be happy to wear it for a week.

Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree

Please turn over

Skin Tone

If you are willing, please tick the box that most closely matches your skin tone:

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Thank you

Thank you very much indeed for your time. The answers you have given will help us understand how to improve the devices for future patients.

What next?

Please place this questionnaire in the packaging with the devices, ready to be sent back to the study team.

¹ Colours obtained from: D'Orazio *et al.*, 'UV radiation and the skin', *Int J Mol Sci.* 2013. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms140612222>. Reproduced under [CC BY 3.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/).